

MALAYSIAN DARKNET ILLICIT MARKETPLACE MONITORING

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July 23, 2018

Abstract

With the emergence of illegal trading especially illicit drugs spreading throughout the darknet marketplaces, there are currently no establish law, policy or enforcement particularly in Malaysia on these dangerous illegal activities that continuously growing. Without a proper knowledge and tools, these illegal transactions on the darknet are difficult to be detected, prevented and controlled, unlike the traditional illegal market trading. Statistics shows that Malaysian are also committed with this crime as some vendors are able to transport these illegal substances from outside into this country and vice versa. Thus, this research main focus is to develop a security forensic monitoring system that will monitor the darknet marketplaces traffic to detect those illegal transactions. The traffic monitoring technique could be achieved by utilizing the machine learning approach which has being used extensively in monitoring encrypted network traffic. Comprehensive studies on machine learning approach are required in developing effective and accurate monitoring system on the darknet marketplaces traffic. Hence, this research objectives are to obtain darknet illegal transaction attributes, to develop full-fledge Support Vector Machine models for illegal transaction classification and to alert the enforcement agencies on detected illegal transactions. By using comprehensive proposed work, it is expected that this research will be able to bridge the knowledge gap on these issues through enhancement of machine

learning models and thus allowing security forensic investigation for illegal substances transaction in darknet marketplace be conducted accordingly. The knowledge obtains are useful for the law enforcement agencies on facing with this evolving type of criminal.

1 INTRODUCTION

Although there are lots of good usage practice, darknet however are also dual-use networks just like other technology such as BitTorrent (where users are not only use it for sharing free materials, they also share copyrighted materials) since it had been exploited for illegal activities purposes. One of the most popular use of the darknet is to access the darknet marketplaces such as SilkRoad and AlphaBay. Darknet marketplaces are digital marketplaces which are located on the darknet. It sells lot of illicit products especially drugs [1]. The use of darknet as a shield allowing the marketplaces to be operated online anonymously. In addition, it facilitates the seller ways to promote their illicit products to the potential buyer without exposing their identities. Due to the strong encryption and privacy protection implemented on the darknet, it is very difficult for the law enforcement agencies to identify, track and monitor these illegal activities [2]. To make things more complicated, the payment transactions utilized the cryptocurrency such as Bitcoin or Ethereum. Cryptocurrency is a subset of digital currency that provided strong anonymity towards the true identities of the entity that involves in the

payment transactions [3]. Thus, it is difficult to identify the transaction related information such as who is involved? where is it happen? and what type of trading being made?

The use of darknets as the mechanism for illicit trading especially on illegal drugs is very destructive technological advancement. With the increasing simplicity of accessing the darknet (only need to install Tor Browser), more and more people starting to access the darknets to browse and to buy illegal items on darknet marketplaces. Even though there are several cases where the law enforcement manages to confiscate these illicit darknet marketplaces, due to the buyer demands, the new marketplaces are continuously emerging to fulfil the needs. This problem has expanded globally as the darknet user worldwide had grown-up over two million just only in year 2017 [4] and show no sign of decreasing. In fact, statistically Malaysian also had been found to be committed in this crime. Research by [5] had found that there are marketplace vendors that transport illegal substance from Malaysia to outside of this country. These striking findings posed many issues to be questioned (i.e. Are they allowed to do that? How to detect their activities? Can we intercept the transactions? Etc).

Although there are many security monitoring mechanisms such as IDPS (Intrusion Detection and Prevention Systems) that are capable to monitor and analyze encrypted traffic, this security tool is not applicable in the darknet network especially in detecting illegal transaction traffic due to strong encryption and privacy-protection facilitated in darknet. To date, there are no specific security approach that are capable to monitor the darknet in detecting these illegal transactions. Hence, there is a corresponding need to look further from security perspective on the interdiction course of these illegal trading in the darknet so that preventive measures can be taken before it becomes extremely difficult to suppress in the future.

Given the aforementioned analysis, this study focus is to develop an effective and accurate security forensic monitoring system to monitor and detect illegal substances transaction in the darknet marketplace using enhanced machine learning approach. Machine learning approaches has been proven to be a reliable and accurate encrypted traffic monitoring mechanism as it has the ability to detect and classify encrypted traffic based on its unique features and characteristics. Therefore, it is a convincing approach to be utilize in monitoring darknet traffic to detect the illegal trading that being carried out in the darknet marketplaces. This monitoring approach also useful in providing the local enforcement agencies with the adequate knowledge on darknet illegal trading, the transactions values and the impact on the Malaysian economic. In addition, it will assist them to monitor and develop security mechanisms or interventions such as the early warning system to prevent illegal drugs spread through the darknet in Malaysia.

To develop a comprehensive security forensic monitoring system using machine learning techniques, there are two main objectives need to be achieved. These objectives are to enhance machine learning models in security forensic monitoring for illegal substances transactions and to define the characteristics of illegal transaction that could be use in classifying the monitored darknet marketplace traffic.

2 PROPOSED WORK

Current machine learning approaches in analyzing monitored encrypted traffic focus merely on the clearnet network without the consideration of the usage on the darknet. Until recently, researcher extended their research on improving the classification capabilities of the encrypted network traffic using the machine learning approaches [6,7]. However, these classifications are lack of attention on the

darknet network traffic especially on the Tor network perspective. Previous works only focus on classification of clearnet network to detect type of encrypted traffic application such as [8-10], and not optimized for the darknet network traffic nor marketplaces transaction characterization. Since no similar work has been reported throughout reviewing the literature, this investigation is a useful reference for other practitioners and researchers interested in the application of analyzing the darknet marketplace traffic for detecting illegal trading.

Based on current literature works, Support Vector Machines (SVM) which is a supervised machine learning approaches appears to be the most suitable machine learning technique to be utilized for the forensic security monitoring system. Based on work by [6] and [7] which utilize SVM has shown promising potential for supervised classification on the darknet marketplace traffic. Hence, this research is aims to enhance these two techniques (SSP-SVM [6] and SVM for parametric discriminators [7]) and combine both techniques to become a full-fledged SVM operator that able to produce better results in classifying monitored illegal transactions on the darknet marketplace traffic. The effectiveness of the previous approaches and the enhanced approach will be further investigated. Finally, the completion of this research will enable the successfulness of the security forensic activities in the darknet.

In this pre-proposal stage of research, there are four proposed stages which are necessary in developing a machine learning-based monitoring system. The proposed stages are currently believed to have potential positive outcome and might be changed in in further studies. The four research stages are:

Stage 1 – Preliminary Study and Analysis

In this stage, all relevant research and literature is reviewed to gain extensive idea on the current

works of the encrypted traffic analyzing models. A study will be conducted to discover the possible issues exist when these existing machine learning approaches being used in darknet. A research gap will be formulated based on the literature reviews.

Stage 2 – Penetration and Transaction Characterization

The darknet marketplaces is monitored using specific network monitoring tools and website crawling tools to capture marketplaces network traffic and gather information on darknet marketplaces website. Then, exploration on security vulnerabilities and mitigations on darknet marketplaces is executed. With the knowledge of these vulnerabilities, the penetration testing process on the darknet marketplace is performed to obtain the marketplaces transaction information. Next, the information obtained throughout the previous processes are analyzed. Thus, initial illegal transaction characteristics on the darknet marketplaces could be defined which are used as a pre-training data in enhancing supervised machine learning approaches in the next stage.

Stage 3 – Design and Implementation

The defined initial characteristics will be pre-processed by performing testing on the existing models using the defined initial characteristics. The classification results from this process will enable the weaknesses of existing models to be learned and intensely analyzed before any enhancement could be made. The two approaches [6, 7] are first enhanced separately toward working effectively in darknet traffic. This is crucial due to the existing SVM approaches are not accustomed to the darknet marketplaces transaction classification.

Then, based on the individual approaches enhancement, the transaction characteristic will be refined further to comprise all the details that

could be produced from stage two activity. Next, the previous enhanced algorithms will be combined and further enhanced for better classification process and signature capabilities on the darknet marketplace traffic. The algorithm will be implemented on a real darknet traffic monitoring environment and its functionality will be tested. This implementation is crucial in benchmarking and comparing the full-fledge SVM with previous machine learning methods. Full-fledge SVM operator is expected to be able to classify and thus detecting darknet marketplace traffic that contain illegal substances transaction.

Stage 4 – Result, Finding and Conclusion

The detected illegal marketplace transaction will be logged and notified to the Enforcement Agencies for further actions. Discussion and conclusion will be incorporated into the final report.

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